

ENGLISH VERSION

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Nigerian Cultural Expressions

Everything Collapses, Everything Transforms into Art

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Nigeria, like the rest of Sub-Saharan Africa, possesses an almost inexhaustible richness of cultural expressions, fundamentally characterized by aesthetic principles that are often distant from Western artistic criteria. In this sense, it is noteworthy that the artistic object cannot be understood solely from a formal aesthetic perspective, but must also be considered in relation to its specific utility, as well as the moral and religious ideas it expresses. This functionality of art is reflected in the fact that in many African languages the same word means both “beautiful” and “good.”

In many cases, the artistic object remains unfinished: this is evident in oral literature, where each performer transforms, adds, or omits certain passages, or, as in the case of sculpture, where its use modifies and completes the work, which otherwise lacks the final value acquired through its use. In addition, in Nigeria, as in the rest of the African continent, there is a strong tendency to combine different cultural expressions within a single event; thus, storytelling is accompanied by music, dance, and theatrical elements.

At the same time, art is closely linked to everyday activities: singing and dancing take place in honor of a notable figure, in public assemblies, weddings, funerals, circumcision ceremonies, celebrations of the *egbe* (a traditional informal Yoruba collective savings system, which may have different names in each region of the subcontinent), and even within the context of agricultural labor.

Nigeria is home to dozens of ethnic groups that possess distinctive cultural traits resulting in great national and local diversity. Today, for example, radio and television programs are broadcast in 25 different languages, such as Yoruba, Igbo, Igala, Edo, Hausa, Fulani, or Ifik, transmitting music and traditional narratives specific to each group. At the same time, each ethnic group also displays cultural traits influenced to varying degrees by European, North American, and/or Arab cultures. In the case of the Igbo, their extensive diaspora has exposed them to extremely diverse cultural influences.

Moreover, while during the colonial period the British government prohibited numerous traditional manifestations, after independence in the 1960s these re-emerged, though in forms

adapted to the new circumstances of the communities. Examples include the *ekpo* and *ekong* youth societies in the southeast, and the *Ogoni* society in the Yoruba and Edo areas of southern Nigeria.

Since 1949, the Nigerian Institute of Music, founded in Onitsha that same year, has specialized in various forms of traditional music. Today, the institutes of African studies at the universities of Ibadan and Ife, as well as the Schools of Fine Arts and Theatre in Zaria and Ibadan, are the main institutions promoting Nigerian traditional arts, particularly dance and poetry.

Music and Dance

Nigeria shares, in traditional music, the basic musical principles of the entire Sub-Saharan region:

- a) outside Western notation, melody, rhythm, and structure are transmitted from musician to musician, although each may introduce variations and interpretations;
- b) rhythm is the central element, through processes of acceleration and superimposition of rhythmic lines that may sound chaotic to ears untrained in this musical tradition;
- c) over a musical pattern, variations are improvised within a cyclical structure.

Music and dance are inseparable cultural expressions of Nigerian everyday life, and each ethnic group possesses its own particularities.